

SPEECH COMPETENCE AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE COGNITIVE PROCESS

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Competence is the range of issues, problems and tasks in the solution of which a specialist is an expert, i.e. has relevant knowledge and personal experience.

Speech competence means knowledge of the ways of forming and formulating thoughts with the help of language, as well as the ability to use language in speech. Some researchers also call this type of competence sociolinguistic competence in order to emphasize the inherent ability to choose the right linguistic form and mode of expression depending on the conditions of the speech act: the situation, communicative goals and intentions of the speaker.

Every lecturer, undoubtedly, should have speech competence, as he/she transmits knowledge to students, and the degree of students' cognitive interest in the subject, and hence motivation, depends on how the lecturer communicates with them. It also determines the effectiveness of students' mastering of subject knowledge and skills influences the culture of interpersonal relations, creates the appropriate moral and psychological climate of the learning process.

Information is transmitted by verbal (speech) and non-verbal (facial expressions, gestures, etc.) means. Speech communication is communication by means of words. A.S. Makarenko believed that a lecturer could become the master only when he learns to pronounce even the simplest words and phrases (for example, "Come here") with 15-20 intonation shades [1].

The ability to use words, to express one's thoughts emotionally is very important and relevant for a teacher, because by managing his/her own speech, he/she manages, to a certain extent, the speech of other subjects of the educational process. This ability to manage is competence.

The study of the content of exemplary programs created based on the federal component of the state standard of basic and secondary (full general education) has shown that it is selected and structured based on the competence approach to learning. Accordingly, all types of competences (communicative, linguistic, linguistic and cultural competences) are formed and developed in grades 5-9, and developed and improved in older grades. All these competences are in an inseparable connection, which provides an integrated approach to the improvement of linguistic and communicative skills and abilities, solving the main task of modern education - the formation and development of a linguistic personality capable of analysing the information contained in the text, creating his/her own speech utterance and applying the results of intellectual activity in practice, i.e. free command of language in different spheres and situations. The linguistic scientist V.V. Vinogradov states: "A high speech culture of a person, his good knowledge and flair for language is the best support, the surest help and the most reliable recommendation for every person in his social and creative activity"[2].

Speech competence is the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for understanding others and generating one's own programs of speech behavior adequate to the goals, spheres, and situation of communication. The following skills are necessary for the formation of speech communication skills:

- ability to understand the topic and comprehend the logic of thought development;
- ability to make a plan;
- ability to extract necessary information from an oral or written source;
- the ability to collect and systematize material.

To form and develop these skills, different teaching methods are used, which are defined as "a system of consecutive interrelated actions of the teacher and the student, ensuring the assimilation of the content of education, the development of mental strength and abilities of students, their mastery of the means of self-education and self-learning. Teaching methods designate the purpose

of learning, the method of assimilation and the nature of interaction between the subjects of learning".

One of the leading methods is the method of person-centered learning, in which the student determines:

- the object of activity;
- form of activity;
- the form of presentation of the received information.

No less important is the method of pedagogical stimulation and development of communicative activity or simulative-motivational method, that is, "a set of means and techniques that encourage the pupil to certain actions.

Among the forms of work that stimulate the development of students' speech competence at lessons, we can name the following: conducting an off-site excursion, drawing up interview questions, defending illustrations, inviting them to read, etc.

There are also various forms of extracurricular work of the stimulative-motivational method: meetings and holidays with parents, excursions and role-playing games for younger students, writing articles in mass media, including school newspapers; field trips and expeditions, work with archival documents and materials in district and regional archives, making crossword puzzles, quizzes, etc.

In the process of work in any of the above-mentioned forms, students observe, recording interesting findings, their state and evaluation of what they have seen, their feelings. These records help students to understand their feelings and sensations, to see their own mistakes in communication with others, to analyse their communicative skills, since oral and written speech as types of speech activity are realised in interrelated speech and thinking processes - perception and reproduction of a statement, conditioned by the situation of communication [3].

The project-research method, undoubtedly based on the above two methods, is widely used in extracurricular activities. This method involves the formation and development of many speech skills:

- planning of activities;

- searching for material in literary and archival sources;
- selection and systematisation of material;
- writing scientific and journalistic style texts, essays;
- editing and improving texts;
- preparation of theses and reports (revision of previously created texts);
- public speaking in different audiences;
- answering questions of opponents.

According to the number of participants in accordance with the personality-oriented method, students' activities can be both individual and group. Such implementation takes into account the interest of students, their psychological characteristics and mutual sympathies, and organises mutual assistance and mutual learning of students of different ages, where everyone can realise their abilities and try themselves in a new capacity.

The methods based on the application of new information technologies are new, but already well proven. Mastering these methods is an integral part of students' education, including their speech competence. IT is used in two ways: as a form of illustrative and visual method and creation of an independent electronic product. In the first case, students have the opportunity to comment on what they have seen, make comments and additions, while independent preparation of presentations also develops such speech skills as understanding the text, highlighting the main points, and planning. Creating an independent product is more complex work, requiring both technical skills and a variety of speech skills for collecting material, systematising and presenting it. They are carried out based on the project-research method [4].

The development of society at the present stage sets a task for educational establishments to make the learning process meaningful for students, of direct, vital interest, which is associated with the humanization of education, and puts forward new requirements for the personality of a school graduate, primarily from the position of socialization and a high level of culture and citizenship.

A high level of human culture, in turn, is inconceivable without a high level of speech culture. We will not make a discovery if we say that language learning is more successful if its study is organically connected with the tasks of speech communication, if conditions are created under which students successfully master the skills of text formation.

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